

Synthesis of Some Aryl Fluorobenzene Sulphonates and Hydroxy Diaryl Sulphones as Potential Fungicides

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Several aryl fluorobenzene sulphonates have been prepared by the interaction of fluorobenzene sulphonylchloride and appropriate phenols. Some of these esters were subjected to Fries transformation in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ in absence of solvent to give hydroxy diaryl sulphones. All these compounds have been tested against two species of fungi, viz. *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Aspergillus niger* and their fungitoxicity have been compared with that of Dithane M-45, a commercial fungicide. While some of the sulphones exhibit fungitoxicity comparable to the commercial fungicide at concentrations of 1000 ppm and 100 ppm, all compounds under investigation turn out to be very weak fungicides at a concentration of 10 ppm.

THE esters of aromatic sulphonic acids often display high physiological activity¹. The commercialisation of Ovotran (I)^{1,2,3} and Genite (II)⁴ as pesticides is an ample proof of biological versatility of such esters. Similarly, diaryl sulphones such as sulphenone⁵ (III) also exhibit pesticidal properties. However, similar data on fluoro and mixed halo-benzene sulphonic acid ester and related hydroxy sulphones appears to be lacking except some preparative work reported by us earlier⁶.

In view of these and also the observation that introduction of fluorine often imparts fungitoxicity in aromatic systems^{7,8,9}, it was anticipated that the aryl esters of fluoro and mixed halo benzene sulphonic acid (IV) might be an useful pesticide and also the hydroxy sulphones (IV) by virtue of possessing the kerolytic phenolic -OH group and the essential features of sulphenone (III) might have enhanced pesticidal properties.

The arylfluorobenzene sulphonates were prepared by reacting fluorobenzene sulphonylchlorides¹⁰ with appropriate phenol in acetone alkali solution in cold⁹. The fluorobenzene sulphonyl chlorides¹⁰

were prepared by chlorosulphonation of fluorobenzenes following the methods of Huntress and Carten¹⁰. The fluoroaromatic hydrocarbons were prepared essentially by Balz-Schiemann reaction¹¹. The hydroxy diarylsulphones were obtained by the Fries transformation of arylfluorobenzene sulphonates at 130-40° in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$.

The significant bands in ir spectra of sulphonates were, 1160-1200 cm^{-1} (O - SO_2 - sym. stretching) and 1010-1040 cm^{-1} (C - F stretching) in addition to bands around 1600, 1550 and 1475 cm^{-1} , characteristic of aromatic ring. For the hydroxy sulphones, it revealed bands around 1300-1333 cm^{-1} (- SO_2 - asym. stretching), 1100-1145 cm^{-1} (- SO_2 - sym. stretching) and an intense peak at 3300-3340 cm^{-1} due to phenolic -OH stretching. Presence of this -OH peak indicates the conversion of sulphonates into hydroxy sulphones.

Experimental

Fluorohydrocarbons: 4-Fluorotoluene¹² b.p. 118-20°, 3-fluorotoluene¹³ b.p. 116° and 4-chloro-fluorobenzene¹⁴ b.p. 130°/756 mm were prepared from *p*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine and *p*-chloroaniline respectively by Balz-Schiemann reaction.

Arylsulphonyl chlorides: 2-Methyl-5-fluorobenzene sulphonyl chloride¹⁰ b.p. 170-72°/40 mm, 2-methyl-4-fluorobenzene sulphonyl chloride¹⁰ b.p. 150-52°/92 mm and 2-chloro-5-fluorobenzene sulphonylchloride¹⁰ b.p. 205°/10 mm were prepared by chlorosulphonation of appropriate fluorohydrocarbons following the method of Huntress and Carten.

These were characterised as sulphonamides.

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Arylfluorobenzene sulphonates: To an ice-cold solution of arylsulphonyl chloride (1.1 M) and phenol (1 M) in acetone, was added a slight excess of NaOH solution (10%) with frequent shaking. The sulphonates thus separating were washed free of alkali and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	m.p. °C
1.	5-F	CH ₃	Cl	Cl	H	65
2.	5-F	CH ₃	Cl	H	H	53
3.	5-F	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	91
4.	5-F	CH ₃	H	Cl	H	68
5.	5-F	CH ₃	H	H	H	62
6.	4-F	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	51
7.	4-F	CH ₃	Cl	H	H	82
8.	4-F	CH ₃	H	H	Cl	80
9.	5-F	Cl	Cl	Cl	H	54
10.	5-F	Cl	H	Cl	H	66

11.	5-F	CH ₃	Cl	Cl	H	165
12.	5-F	CH ₃	Cl	H	H	114
13.	5-F	CH ₃	H	Cl	H	210
14.	4-F	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	170
15.	5-F	Cl	Cl	Cl	H	190

Satisfactory elemental analysis were obtained for all the compounds.

Hydroxy diaryl sulphonates: A mixture of arylfluorobenzene-sulphonate (0.1 M) and anhydrous AlCl₃ (0.15 M) was heated till a melt was formed. Heating of the melt was continued for 3-4 hr at 130-40°. The reaction mixture was decomposed with crushed ice and HCl. The product separating was taken into ether and purified as usual. The sulphonates thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Fungicidal activity: The fungicidal activity was evaluated by agar growth technique¹⁴ on *H. oryzae* and *A. niger* at three different concentrations,

1000 ppm, 100 ppm and 10 ppm. With a view to compare the results, a commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was also tested under similar conditions.

The fungicidal data of compounds under investigation reveal that the sulphonate esters as a class are very weak fungicides. The hydroxy sulphonates are toxic to both *H. oryzae* and *A. niger* at higher concentrations (1000 ppm and 100 ppm). The activity is particularly more pronounced in those sulphonates which contain chloro substituents in *para* and *ortho*-positions or both. However, all these compounds prove to be weaker fungicides at a concentration of 10 ppm.

The presence of fluorine does not in any way enhance the toxicity of such compounds. The mixed halo derivatives, however, have better performance as fungicide than those containing fluoro or chloro separately. It is noteworthy that the fungitoxicity of the compounds is greater towards *A. niger* than *H. oryzae*.

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